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STUDY ON ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF *CURCUMA CAESIA*

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ABSTRACT

Rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia*, commonly known as Kali Haldi/Black Turmeric, available in many parts of India has many medicinal properties. *Curcuma caesia* reported for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic properties in many studies but very few studies done for its potential anthelmintic activity. Hence, our present study aimed at reporting the anthelmintic properties of *Curcuma caesia*. For the present study, three extracts (ethanol, chloroform and aqueous) of rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia* at three concentrations (25mg/dl, 50mg/dl, 100mg/dl) of each extract was studied for anthelmintic property. Albendazole (20mg/dl) was taken as standard. Anthelmintic study include, determining the time taken for paralysis and death of earthworms in the presence of test samples. The results indicated that the most effective sample for inducing paralysis in earthworms is ethanolic extract (100mg/dl) by 18.06±0.74 min and chloroform extract (100mg/dl) by 16.24±0.86 min, and among the three extracts, ethanolic extract (100mg/dl) is effective in causing death in 36.81±1.13min. Whereas the standard Albendazole (20mg/dl) caused paralysis of earthworms in 23.09±1.56 min and death in 37.20± 1.74 min. The present study reveals that rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia* have potential vermifuge activity than vermucidal activity in comparison with satandard Albendazole in a dose dependent manner.

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INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants in India are used from centuries as important therapeutic source for treating variety of ailments and has been found to have immense Global importance. Their importance is growing now a day, as many people prefer to use natural drugs with less side effect profile than synthetic drugs. India is perhaps the largest producer in the world for medicinal plants and is called Botanical garden of the world [1].

Curcuma linn is a largest genus belonging to the family *Zingiberaceae*. It comprises about 70-80 species of rhizomatous annual or perinial herbs cultivated all over the world. Out of these about 40 species are cultivated in India. The genus *Curcuma* has a paramount importance as spices, dyes, cosmetics etc., *Curcuma* is gaining importance as a potential source of new drugs [2-4]. *Curcuma caesia* is one of this family commonly called as Black Turmeric/ Kali Haldi. It was been used by many tribe communities in the world from centuries as spice, medicine and in spiritual practices. *Curcuma caesia* is a perinial herb with bluish-black rhizomes found in north east central India. The plant also found in Papi hills of East Godavari and Khammam districts of Andhra Pradesh, North hill forest of Sikkim [5]. Traditionally, rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia* are used in the treatment of hemorrhoids, leukoderma, leprosy, asthma, bronchitis, cancer, epilepsy, fever, wound, vomiting, menstrual disorder, smooth muscle relaxant activity, anthelmintic, aphrodisiac, inflammation, gonorrheal discharges, etc. [6,7]. In Manipur, the paste of *Curcuma caesia* rhizomes applied on bruises, rheumatic pains. In Arunachal Pradesh, the fresh decoction of rhizome is used as an anti diarrhoetic and the fresh paste of rhizome is applied over snake and scorpion bite.

Helminthiasis is most common infection of humankind affecting large proportions of the world. Helminth parasites live in the gut of humans and harm the host in many ways like blood loss in the stools, mall absorption, secreting toxins etc., and any drug, which eliminate such parasites, called as anthelmintic drug and there are many drugs available in the market. Now a day's resistance against many drugs have reported and hence there is a need for search of new drugs with less side effects [8, 9]. *Curcuma caesia* was reported for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic properties in many studies but very few studies were done for its potential anthelmintic activity [10-12]. Based on traditional information available on *Curcuma caesia* our present study aimed at reporting the anthelmintic properties of *Curcuma caesia*.

Aim & Objectives:

- To conduct preliminary phytochemical tests
- To study entitled "Study on Anthelmintic activity of *Curcuma caesia*" using Indian adult earth worms, *Pheretima posthuma* as model.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection of Plant material:

Fresh rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia* were purchased online from north India and were identified and authenticated at Department of Botany, SIMS College of Life Sciences, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Plant extract preparation:

The rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia* were washed in distilled water and shade -dried at room temperature. Dried rhizomes were crushed to coarse powder in electric blender and subjected to extraction by using Soxhlet's extractor. By using successive solvent extraction, dried powdered rhizomes material was extracted with, ethanol, chloroform and aqueous solvents. The extracts dried at low temperature under reduced pressure.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis:

For the extracts of ethanol, chloroform and aqueous extracts of *Curcuma cassia*, preliminary phytochemical tests carried out using standard method gave the following results depicted in table-1.

Worm collection:

Indian adult earth worms *Pheretima posthuma* collected from vermiculture plant, Agriculture department, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh. All the earthworms washed with normal saline to remove mud and fecal matter. The length of earthworms selected for the experimental study are 5 cm length and width 0.1-0.2cm.

Sample preparation:

Test samples of ethanol, chloroform, aqueous extracts of *Curcuma caesia* prepared separately by dissolving and suspending 2 mg of aqueous extract respectively in minimum amount of 0.2% v/v of Tween 20 as a suspending agent. The volume adjusted to 20ml with normal saline to obtain concentration of 25 µg/ml, 50 µg/ml and 100 µg/ml for each type of extract. Albendazole of 20 mg/ml taken as a standard drug for the study.

Anthelmintic activity:

The earthworms used for the study, as they have anatomical and physiological resemblance with intestinal roundworm parasites in humans for preliminary evaluation of anthelmintic activity [13-15]. Earthworms of nearly equal size selected and divided in to 11 groups each group containing 6 earthworms. The earth worms were release in to 20 ml of different samples as given in the table-2 , G1 is treated with control, G2 with standard drug, and other groups with 25 mg/ mL, 50 mg/mL and 100 mg/mL concentration of ethanol, chloroform, and aqueous extracts. Observations made for the time taken for paralysis or death of individual worms. Paralysis was said to occur when the worms do not revive even in normal saline. Death was concluded when the worms lose their motility followed with fading away of their body color. Albendazole (20 mg/mL) was used as standard while normal saline as control. All the results expressed as Mean \pm SEM of six animals in each group [16].

RESULTS & DISCUSSION**Phytochemical tests:**

Preliminary phytochemical tests conducted for the three extracts of *Curcuma caesia* revealed the presence of chemical constituents depicted in Table-1. The results showed the presence of carbohydrates, saponins, glycosides, phytosterols, resins, tannins and flavonoids.

Table-1 Phytochemical investigations of *Curcuma caesia* extracts.

Chemical constituent	Test	<i>Curcuma caesia</i> extracts		
		Ethanol	Chloroform	Aqueous
Carbohydrate test	Molisch's test	-	-	+
	Benedict's test	+	+	-
Glycosides	Fehlings test	+	+	-
	Borntrager's test	+	-	-
Saponins	Legal test	+	+	+
Phytosterols	Froth test	+	+	+
	Salkowski's test	-	+	+
	Tshugajeu test	+	+	-
Phenols	Acetone- water test	+	-	-
Tannins	Ferric chloride test	-	+	-
Flavonoids	Gelatin test	-	+	-
	Alkaline reagent test	+	+	-
	Lead acetate	-	-	-

Anthelmintic activity:

The results of present study to determine the anthelmintic activity of rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia*, depicted in table-2.

Table-2 Effect of *Curcuma caesia* on paralysis and death time of earthworms.

Sl.No.	Treatment	Group	Concentration (mg/mL)	Time of paralysis (min)(mean \pm SEM)	Time of death (min)(mean \pm SEM)
1.	Control	I	-	-	-
2.	Albendazole	II	20	23.09 \pm 1.56	37.20 \pm 1.74
3.	Ethololic extract	III	25	35 \pm 1.56**	70.66 \pm 1.15
		IV	50	26.15 \pm 1.4**	50.15 \pm 0.95
4.	Chloform extract	V	100	18.06 \pm 0.74**	36.81 \pm 1.13
		VI	25	26.41 \pm 1.44**	79.28 \pm 0.99
5.	Aqueous extract	VII	50	19.26 \pm 0.99**	62.97 \pm 1.48
		VIII	100	16.24 \pm 0.86**	51.69 \pm 1.11
		IX	25	86.04 \pm 0.88**	148.41 \pm 1.50
		X	50	50.60 \pm 0.69**	132.72 \pm 1.44
		XI	100	34.28 \pm 0.90**	120.89 \pm 1.22

Values expressed as mean \pm SEM, one way ANOVA. n=6 in each group. **P<0.01.

Vermifuge activity:

From the observations of table-2, ethanolic and chloroform, extracts exhibited an effective vermifuge activity than aqueous extract in comparison with the standard Albendazole. Ethanolic extract at concentration 100mg/dl, induced paralyzes in earthworms by 18.06 \pm 0.74min and chloroform extract at a concentration of 100mg/dl induced paralyzes in earthworms by 16.24 \pm 0.86min where the standard albendazole induced by 23.09 \pm 1.56min.

Vermicidal activity:

From the observations of table-2, ethanolic extracts at concentration 100mg/dl, caused death of earthworms by 36.81 ± 1.13 min, where as the standard aAbendazole cause death in 37.20 ± 1.74 min.

DISCUSSION

In the present work, phytochemical investigation was done which revealed the quality of major class of constituents. Paralysis of earthworm was most affected by the extracts of *Curcuma caesia*. Hence, in the present study it was found that *Curcuma caesia* an effective vermifuge than a vermicide. Further studies are required to identify the actual chemical constituents that are present in the crude extracts of *Curcuma caesia* which are responsible for anthelmintic activity and to establish the effectiveness and pharmacological

CONCLUSION

Paralysis of earthworm was most affected by the extracts of *Curcuma caesia* than death. Hence, the present study reveals that rhizomes of *Curcuma caesia* have potential vermifuge activity than vermicidal activity in comparision with satandard Albendazole. These activities may be due to presence of phytoconstituents in ethanolic, chloroform and aqueous extracts. As crude extracts were used in the present study the appropriate phytochemical constituents responsible for the anthelmintic activity is not clearly understood . Hence further studies are recommended. Finally, this work revealed that *Curcuma caesia* have an effective anthelmintic activity and a gift of nature to humankind. This study may provide consolidated information to researchers, as well as practitioners. However, future studies recommended for isolation of phytochemical as well as elucidate the mechanisms behind its anthelmintic effects.

Abbreviations:

SEM - Standard error of the mean

ANOVA - Analysis of variance

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Conflicts of interest: None

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